

Stepwise Stability Constants of Trivalent La, Ce, Pr and Sm Complexes of N,N-Bis(2-Hydroxyethyl) Glycine

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The complexation of La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Sm^{3+} ions with N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl) glycine has been studied by potentiometric titration technique in aqueous medium. All these metal ions form 1:1 and 1:2 complexes in the pH range 4.0-8.0 with considerable overlapping. The log K values are determined at 20°, 30° and 40° at ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO_4) by applying Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum method. The stability constants follow the order: $\text{Sm(III)} > \text{Pr(III)} > \text{Ce(III)} > \text{La(III)}$.

SAXENA and co-workers²⁻⁴ have studied several metal complexes of amino acids which have found useful application in biological¹ and pharmaceutical fields. The present communication describes the complex formation of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Sm(III) with N,N-bis(2-hydroxyethyl) glycine and determination of their stability constants at different temperatures in aqueous solution at a constant ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO_4).

Experimental

N,N-Bis(2-hydroxyethyl) glycine (HA) was obtained from B.D.H. Poole, England. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Fresh solutions of metal ions $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{PrCl}_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, were prepared in calculated quantities of HClO_4 to check hydrolysis. The metal content was estimated by standard methods⁵. The entire study was carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen and fresh solutions were used to avoid any effect of ageing and oxidation.

The experimental procedure involved a series of pH metric titrations of 4mM HA containing 4mM HClO_4 in absence and presence of 1,2,4 mM metal ion against standard (0.1M) NaOH.

pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal digital pH-meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly (accuracy ± 0.1 pH). The temperature of the cell was maintained by thermostat (U_s -type, German) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Requisite quantities of NaClO_4 were added to the solution mixtures for maintaining the constant ionic strength (0.1M). The final volumes of all the mixtures were maintained at 25 ml with doubly-distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of metal ion and HA, the magnitude of

proton displacement was determined by titrating the solution containing metal ion and HA in different ratios against 0.1M NaOH.

The inflection at $m=1$ in free ligand titration curve (Fig. 1, curve 1) corresponds to the titrability of the proton of $-\text{COOH}$ group under experimental conditions which was present in a 'Zwitter ion' form. The addition of an equimolar concentration of metal ion greatly alters the shape of free ligand

Fig. 1. pH titrations of the solutions: Curve (1) 4.0 mM HA, (2) 4.0 mM HA + 1.0 mM Ce(III), (3) 4.0 mM HA + 2.0 mM Ce(III), (4) 4.0 mM HA + 4.0 mM Ce(III), (5) Hydrolysis curve: (a) 4 mM HClO_4 , (b) 4 mM HClO_4 + 1mM Ce(III).

titration curve (Fig. 1, curve 4) indicating the complex formation resulting in the lowering of the buffer region due to proton displacement.

where M^{3+} stands for La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Sm^{3+} .

The inflection at $m=2$ (m being the moles of NaOH per mole of HA) suggests the formation of $M(A)_2$ as the highest complex alongwith MA_3 and $M(OH)_3$ at higher pH values (≈ 9.0).

With a view to study the possibility of formation of hydroxo-complexes, the hydrolysis of the title metal salts was performed. Curve 5, Fig. 1 shows the hydrolysis curve of cerous salt taken as a representative case (hydrolysis curves of other metal salts have not been given for the sake of brevity).

It is observed from these curves that no hydroxo-complexes are formed upto the pH range 7.92, 7.77, 7.47 and 7.40 for La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Sm^{3+} salts respectively.

When metal ion and ligand are mixed in the ratio 1:4, 1:2 and 1:1, the inflections are obtained at $m=0.5$, 1.0 and 2.0 respectively. These inflections suggest the formation of $M(A)^{+2}$ and $M(A)_2^+$ corresponding to 1:1 and 1:2 complexes respectively with considerable overlapping according to the following equations :

i.e., 1:1 and 1:2 complexes are formed simultaneously and in all the above cases metal-complexes may disproportionate at higher pH (≈ 9.0) to give normal metal hydroxide.

Stability constants: Calvin and Melchior's⁸ extension of Bjerrum's method⁶ has been employed for the determination of stability constants of the complexes. The pH titrations of HA solution of ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$ ($NaClO_4$) and $HClO_4$ concentration ($4mM$) for initial lowering of buffer region in absence and presence of metal ion were carried out at 20°, 30° and 40° against 0.1M NaOH and concentration of the bound ligand, calculated from the horizontal distance between the corresponding curves, was divided by the total metal ion concentration to obtain formation function \bar{n} . At any pH, the value of free ligand concentration $[A]$ was calculated from the relation

$$[A] = \frac{[Ligand]_{total} - [Ligand]_{bound}}{[H^+]/K_a + 1}$$

where K_a , the dissociation constant⁷ of HA is 8.318×10^{-9} . The formation curves obtained at different temperatures by plotting \bar{n} vs pA reveal the overlapping formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes for all the four metals La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Pr^{3+} and Sm^{3+} . Hence k_1 and K_2 values were evaluated by graphical methods⁶. The log K values are stated in Table 1. The stabilities of complexes follow the order (Table 1). $Sm(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III)$. A plausible explanation for this trend is the lanthanide contraction as these metals normally form ionic compounds.

TABLE 1—LOGARITHMS OF STEPWISE METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS[@] OF La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) AND Sm(III) COMPLEXES OF N,N-bis(2-HYDROXYETHYL) GLYCINE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES ($\mu=0.1M NaClO_4$)

Metal Ion	20°		30°		40°	
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
La(III)	5.90	3.92	5.01	3.15	4.83	3.01
Ce(III)	5.45	4.01	5.30	3.91	5.13	3.79
Pr(III)	5.98	4.02	5.84	3.62	5.64	3.35
Sm(III)	6.77	4.76	6.51	4.56	6.06	4.45

@ uncertainty limit ± 0.04 units in the log scale.

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